

Study on the Rise of Co-Working in India and its Impacts on Business

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Abstract

With the rise in technology and the scarcity of space in cramped urban cities, Coworking is the next big thing for business corporates and professionals. Co working spaces are shared workplaces by various kinds of business professionals and freelancers.

It is the new age workstyle which has attracted the attention of businesses and individuals alike. But do the benefits of this new age practice outweigh that of traditional workspaces? This Paper aims at identifying the benefits derived from this practice to all the parties involved. With the use of secondary data we aim to analyse the growth of coworking industry in India and its future.

Introduction

Innovation generally refers to changing processes or creating more effective processes, products and ideas. For businesses, this could mean implementing new ideas, even creating a new a working environment for doing business.

The latest trend in the business or the way of doing Business is the Coworking Space or the Co-working Environment. What is a work environment? It is the physical environment in which an employee works. A Coworking space involves a shared workplace, often an office and Independent Activity. How does a work space affect the employees? It Can Affect their Well-Being. The current workforce, would accept a lower salary if it meant working for a company with a strong corporate culture and focus on work-life balance. Culture and Balance begin with the values you foster in your workplace.

History

DeKoven launched the word “coworking” as a way to identify a method that would facilitate collaborative work and business meetings coordinated by computers. He introduced this in 1999.

Software engineer Brad Neuberg was the first one who put this idea to action in 2005 with the San Francisco Coworking Space.

How It Works?

Co working facility is self -employed. Majority business use the space to provide employees with equipment, space and services that they could not otherwise afford or access. Larger enterprises sometimes use coworking facilities to provide office space when they

have more than the normal number of employees working at any given time. It provides an office-like environment but with added flexibility and feasibility.

Coworking provides workspaces in various ways. Some facilities, are cooperatively managed spaces run as non-profit organizations. Other models include flat-rate memberships and fee structures based on access for a single visit or a certain number of days per week, month or year. Most coworking facilities offer a number of options to suit individual needs. Some organizations have multiple locations that members can access. Others provide “coworking visas” that provide free access to partnered facilities in different locations.

Objectives

1. To analyse the benefits of coworking space
2. To compare market positions of co working space in India
3. To estimate future trends and growth of coworking in India

Review of Literature

According to **A. Gandini (2015)**, 52% of coworkers have reported that their earnings went up after participating in coworking spaces.

Moriset’s (2014) study reports 2,498 mapped spaces in 80 countries worldwide. Coworking has spread over all continents, and all kinds of economies. Advanced economies take the lion’s share, with about 1100 spaces in Europe and 860 in North America, but some emerging countries such as Brazil are doing well.

Capdevila (2013) offers a theory of coworking spaces as ‘microclusters’ that enable knowledge transfer among members from a network-based perspective.

Coworking Scenario Abroad

Around the world coworking has been picking up pace and has grown exponentially. The number of spaces has grown by 3050% since 2010 and the number of people working in these space have grown by 8000% .

<u>USA</u>	<u>227</u>	<u>Spain</u>	<u>20</u>	<u>Belgium</u>	<u>8</u>
<u>United Kingdom</u>	<u>30</u>	<u>Italy</u>	<u>13</u>	<u>Mexico</u>	<u>8</u>
<u>Canada</u>	<u>28</u>	<u>Brazil</u>	<u>12</u>	<u>Portugal</u>	<u>7</u>
<u>France</u>	<u>27</u>	<u>Argentina</u>	<u>10</u>	<u>Netherlands</u>	<u>6</u>
<u>Germany</u>	<u>24</u>	<u>Australia</u>	<u>9</u>		

In London, a new coworking space opens every 5 days and every 7.5 days one opens in New York. This shows the speed at which these spaces are coming up.

Europe is forecast to see 255 million square feet of flexible space in 2019, which represents a 12% increase. As of 2019, Asia Pacific has the largest number of coworking spaces.

Coworking in India

India is one of the fastest growing economies in the world. The past decade has seen a remarkable growth in the number of startups in our country. But to add to this growth is the high rate of

rent inflation in metropolitan cities with Mumbai at the top at 18%, followed by Chennai and Bangalore at 15% and 14% respectively. Coworking Spaces eliminates the operating cost incurred for procuring an office. These costs are said to be approximately 9% - 12% of total costs. It helps businesses focus on core activities rather than real estate. Coworking improves the networking of people. Their social circle grows with people from diverse backgrounds but common ideals and goals. 83% have reported an increase in their business network. 74% of coworkers have claimed a rise in their productivity owing to flexible and diverse working conditions.

Source: Deskwanted

This further proves the positive impact it makes on the coworkers, improving their interpersonal skills and making them more productive.

The Coworking Industry is one of the fastest growing sectors. It is expected to grow 4 to 8 times the size of the current industry in 2019. Currently there are 18700 Coworking spaces around the world and around 450 spaces all over India.

Some of the prominent players in India are shown in the table below. They account to nearly 60% of spaces in the country.

Name	No. of Cities	No. of Centres
Regus	14	113
Wework	3	9
Springboard	7	17
Social	3	15
Bhive	1	6
Awfis	3	28
Innov8	2	10
Insta Office	4	10
MYHQ	1	60
Total	38	268

This growth is visible in all Tier I and Tier II cities across the country. These companies are using big-data generated from their existing facilities to better understand their facilities. There is constant feedback helping the operator understand the needs of the occupier and also make smart investment decisions. Awfis is the first of many to have an App that enables people to book office spaces on real-time basis. This data-driven method helps these spaces to expand at high rates with greater chances of success.

Findings and Suggestions

Our study shows that coworking spaces have grown exponentially over the past few years. The reason behind more and more people choosing coworking spaces is increased productivity, flexibility, expansion of social and business network. Coworking helps improve the health and well being of the coworkers. Also it is cost efficient pushing more startups and corporate giants to opt for this as it is better for their balance sheet. The future would see a rise in the number of large companies going for coworking rather than traditional offices to give their employees an upper hand and to diversify their work culture through the networking that these spaces provide. The next few years would see a new era of coworking in India. With government schemes like Make in India, there is an increase in the number of MSMEs. The office requirements of these companies will be catered by the coworking industry. The coworking market in India is being dominated by a few large players currently, however the growth aspects of these industries would promote more investments and many more operators to flourish in the next few years.

In our opinion, support from the government can lower the cost involved in procuring coworking spaces. It can also boost the industry and improve and regulate participation from private players.

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